

28 March 2025 Myanmar Earthquake: Strong Ground Motions, Macroseismic Intensity, Liquefaction, and ALOS-2 ScanSAR Remote Sensing Damage Observations

Alejandro Cruz^{1,2}, Mohammad Ghasemi³, Shaghayegh Karimzadeh^{*1}, Sadra Karimzadeh^{3,4}, Aysegul Askan⁵, Masashi Matsuoka⁴, and Paulo B. Lourenço¹

Abstract

On 28 March 2025, a devastating M 7.7 earthquake struck Myanmar along the right-lateral strike-slip Sagaing fault, followed by an M 6.7 aftershock twelve minutes later. This study presents a comprehensive assessment of the earthquake's effects through recorded strong ground motions, macroseismic intensity observations, secondary hazards including liquefaction, and remote sensing-based damage detection. The supershear rupture spanned ~460 km, with pronounced fault directivity effects resulting in high peak ground acceleration values of up to 0.57g recorded for the horizontal components and macroseismic intensities reaching modified Mercalli intensity = X in nearby cities. Analysis of acceleration time series and Fourier amplitude spectra at nearby recording stations revealed significant near-field effects and spectral exceedances over Myanmar National building code design levels, particularly in the short-period range, affecting mostly low-rise structures. Secondary hazard evaluation indicates widespread liquefaction, especially near the Irrawaddy River, supported by correlations between cumulative absolute velocity and liquefaction probability maps. Remote sensing analysis using multitemporal Advanced Land Observation Satellite-2 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) coherence data identified severe building and road damage in urban centers. A differential coherence method, coupled with urban masking and OpenStreetMap road data, enabled spatial quantification of damage, revealing over 39,000 km of roads and 306 km² of buildings with moderate-to-heavy damage. The results provide critical insight into the earthquake's impact and demonstrate the joint evaluation of ground-motion analysis and SAR-based damage mapping for rapid seismic response.

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Introduction

Myanmar is located in a seismically active region with earthquakes primarily resulting from two main causes, as shown in Figure 1: (1) the subduction of the northward-moving India plate beneath the Burma plate, transitioning to a collision zone in the north, along the Andaman megathrust at a rate of 2–3.5 cm/yr; and (2) the northward motion of the Burma plate, driven by seafloor spreading in the Andaman Sea, occurring at a rate of 2.5–3.0 cm/yr (Thein *et al.*, 2009). An earthquake of M 7.7 occurred in Myanmar on 28 March 2025, followed by a second event of M 6.7 twelve minutes later. The earthquakes occurred on the Sagaing fault, which lies between the Burma microplate and the Sunda plates as a main strike-slip fault system (e.g., Gögen *et al.*, 2024). The same fault caused destructive

1. Department of Civil Engineering, University of Minho, ISISE, ARISE, Guimarães, Portugal, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5631-0548> (AC); <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3753-1676> (ShK); <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8459-0199> (PBL); 2. School of Civil Engineering and Geomatics, Universidad del Valle, G-7, Cali, Colombia;
3. Remote Sensing Laboratory, Department of Remote Sensing and GIS, University of Tabriz, Tabriz, Iran, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6992-2893> (MG); <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5645-0188> (SaK); 4. Department of Architecture and Building Engineering, Institute of Science Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3061-5754> (MM); 5. Civil Engineering and Earthquake Studies Departments, Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Türkiye, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4827-9058> (AA)

*Corresponding author: shaghkn@civil.uminho.pt

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Figure 1. Tectonic map of Myanmar and nearby regions, highlighting major fault systems, plate boundaries, the epicenter of the 28 March 2025 **M** 7.7 earthquake (yellow star), seismic stations (blue triangles), together with the Advanced Land Observation Satellite (ALOS)-2 PALSAR-2 data footprint used in this study (red box). Base map taken from [Thein et al. \(2009\)](#). The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

events in the past, such as the 1930 **M** 7.3, 1946 **M** 7.7, and 1956 **M** 7.0 earthquakes. The 2025 **M** 7.7 event caused a super-shear rupture of 460 km ([Shahzada et al., 2025](#)).

With Advanced Land Observation Satellite (ALOS)-2 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data, extensive damage to the built environment during the 2025 Myanmar event in the cities of Mandalay, Sagaing, and Naypyidaw was observed due to near-field effects coupled with vulnerable building structures in the region. The ALOS-2 footprint covers a significant portion of central Myanmar (red area in Fig. 1), spanning from $\sim 94^\circ$ to 99° E longitude and 21° to 25° N latitude.

The macroseismic intensity values in the nearby urban centers reached modified Mercalli intensity (MMI) values of X. The directivity effects were clearly observed, including larger recorded peaks in the forward direction as well as a skyscraper collapsing in Bangkok, Thailand. This collapse may also be attributed to the soft soil conditions and potential basin effects ([Qodri, 2018](#)).

Given the scale of the event and the diversity of its impacts, a comprehensive assessment combining seismological data, macroseismic observations, secondary hazard mapping, and satellite-based damage detection is critical. This multidisciplinary study aims to document and analyze the ground-motion characteristics, evaluate the extent and nature of infrastructure damage, and investigate the geospatial patterns of secondary hazards, particularly liquefaction, using remote sensing techniques. The article presents ground-motion data and key insights from strong-motion records and macroseismic intensity. It also investigates secondary hazards, particularly liquefaction susceptibility and its spatial patterns, using geospatial indicators. Next, remote sensing analysis is conducted to map damage to roads and buildings using ALOS-2 SAR data. The study concludes by summarizing the main findings and their relevance for improving earthquake response and hazard mitigation strategies in the region.

Observations on Recorded Strong Ground Motions and Macroseismic Intensity Values

The mainshock was recorded at six strong ground motion stations within a 370 km rupture distance (R_{rup}) with rapidly varying peak ground-motion parameters (Fig. 2). Selected stations that recorded the 28 March 2025 **M** 7.7 Myanmar earthquake, including observed (Fig. 2a) peak ground acceleration (PGA), (Fig. 2b) peak ground velocity (PGV), (Fig. 2c) pseudospectral acceleration (PSA) ($T = 0.2$ s), and (Fig. 2d) PSA ($T = 1.0$ s). (The surface projection of the fault is also presented).

From the spatial distribution of the recorded data, it is observed that PGA, PGV, and PSA with 5% damping ratio values are lower north of the epicenter and much larger in the south. This observation is attributed to the fault directivity effects on the causative fault, which is the right-lateral strike-slip Sagaing fault segment. Despite the lack of data in the near field, it is observed that the maximum horizontal PGA reaches $0.57g$ at the closest station to the rupture with a corresponding short-period PSA value of almost 1.0g.

In this study, we present detailed information on the recorded strong ground motions at the six nearest stations with reliable data and assess the recorded motions (Table 1). The information includes station coordinates, rupture distance (R_{rup}), epicentral distance (R_{epi}), elevation, PGA, PGV, Housner intensity (HI), significant duration (D_{5-95}) within 5% and 95% of Arias intensity (I_A), and cumulative absolute velocity (CAV). The raw data are obtained from the Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology website ([Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology \[IRIS\], 2025](#)), baseline corrected, and filtered with a fourth-order Butterworth filter between 0.1 and 30 Hz. There is no precise information on the site classes or V_{S30} values of the stations; only general information about V_{S30} is discussed later in the secondary hazard section; however, the elevations of the

stations on the tectonic map allow us to establish a framework. From Table 1, it is observed that the stations within close distances from the rupture located along the forward direction on low elevations experienced larger ground motions, whereas the farther stations and those on the mountain edge recorded much smaller motions.

We focus on the three closest stations to evaluate the acceleration time series and Fourier amplitude spectra (FAS) in Figures 3–5. On the same plots, we also compare the recorded response spectra (PSA) to the corresponding design spectra of Myanmar with 5% damping for a return period of 475 yr in the Myanmar National Building Code (MNBC) (2020). Among

Figure 2. Selected stations that recorded the 28 March 2025 **M** 7.7 Myanmar earthquake, including observed (a) peak ground acceleration (PGA), (b) peak ground velocity (PGV), (c) pseudo-spectral acceleration (PSA) ($T = 0.2$ s), and (d) PSA ($T = 1.0$ s). (The surface projection of the fault is also presented). The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

the recording stations, the NPW station is located at an R_{rup} of 2.75 km. The recorded PGA values in the horizontal directions are 511.5 cm/s^2 (east–west) and 603.45 cm/s^2 (north–south) with corresponding PGV values of 96.97 and 93.94 cm/s, respectively. The vertical component is almost

TABLE 1

Information on the Recorded Stations

Station	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)	R_{rup} (km)	R_{epi} (km)	Elevation (m)	Channel	PGA (cm/s ²)	PGV (cm/s)	HI (cm)	D_{5-95} (s)	I_A (cm/s)	CAV (cm/s)
NPW	19.779° N	96.138° E	2.75	265.89	158	HNE	511.47	96.97	288.2	13.4	2.78	1625.12
						HNN	603.45	93.94	300.1	13.2	3.13	1621.48
						HNZ	1111.9	65.56	228.7	9.9	3.3	1351.84
TGI	20.768° N	97.034° E	Not available	192.29	1457.5	HHE	81.13	3.35	15.5	51.8	0.26	857.17
						HHN	73.95	2.63	14.6	49.0	0.2	754.29
						HHZ	41.75	3.01	12.6	42.7	0.05	340.57
NGU	21.206° N	94.917° E	113.95	147.15	70.4	HNE	45	6.2	31.1	65.7	0.096	588.60
						HNN	58.1	8.87	35.1	72.2	0.09	557.04
						HNZ	17.65	4.5	12.1	100.4	0.02	359.60
YGN	16.865° N	96.153° E	157.14	607.07	20	HNE	24.3	11.7	24.75	118.5	0.04	437.95
						HNN	14.7	7.8	18.08	118.1	0.04	499.16
						HNZ	19.5	3.7	15.24	120.8	0.01	256.51
CHTO	18.814° N	98.944° E	272.22	506.00	420	HN1	9.52	5.9	8.66	33.85	0.004	104.18
						HN2	8.21	3.97	9.26	34.97	0.004	114.77
						HNZ	12.9	4.44	10.83	33.41	0.005	118.65
KTN	21.286° N	99.590° E	370.59	416.70	832	HNE	10.63	2.54	12.18	87.31	0.015	267.78
						HNN	13.22	4.48	16.82	90.76	0.024	332.03
						HNZ	7.31	1.87	9.97	86.69	0.006	165.93

Channel, components of recorded ground motion: HH, high frequency and high sensitivity; HN, high gain, high-sampling rate; E, east–west direction; N, north–south direction; Z, vertical direction; 1, east–west direction; 2, north–south direction. CAV, cumulative absolute velocity; D_{5-95} , significant duration (time between 5% and 95% of Arias intensity); HI, Housner intensity; I_A , Arias intensity; PGA, peak ground acceleration; PGV, peak ground velocity; R_{epi} , epicentral distance; and R_{rup} , closest distance to rupture.

twice the horizontal component, attributed to the near-field source effects such as those observed in the 2023 Kahramanmaraş sequence (Altindal and Askan, 2024). At the NPW station, D_{5-95} of the horizontal components is around 13 s at this station, HI is 288 cm and 300 cm in the east–west and north–south directions, respectively. Such high levels of HI usually correlate closely with structural damage (e.g., Askan et al., 2022). At station NPW, there are strong near-field effects as observed in the form of velocity pulses, also consistent with the enhanced low-frequency content in the FAS.

The final observation is on the comparison of the acceleration response spectra (PSA) against the design spectra defined in the MNBC (2020) with 5% damping for a return period of 475 yr. As the station is located at a low elevation, we use the design spectra for sites C and D for the sake of comparison. It is noted that, according to the national building code MNBC (2020), the short-period site coefficient (F_a) is the same for site classes C and D, which explains the similarity of spectral values in the plateau. The difference between classes C and D appears in the long-period site coefficient (F_v), which controls velocity-dominated site effects.

It is observed that the recorded response spectra exceed the design spectra for both type C and D soils, up to periods of 0.3 s. This observation, coupled with the structural vulnerability, could have caused damage to the low-rise residential buildings. Within $T = 0.3-1.3$ s range, the recorded spectra are below the design spectra. For the longer periods, again, the recorded horizontal spectra exceed the corresponding design amplitudes.

Station TGI is located in the fault-normal direction, east of the Sagaing fault at an R_{epi} of 192.29 km. From the map, this station is at an elevation of 1457.5 m. As a result of the hard-rock conditions and increased distances, both PGA and PGV values are much lower than those recorded at the station NPW. The recorded PGA values are 81.13 cm/s² in the east–west and 73.95 cm/s² in the north–south directions. The vertical PGA is almost half of that of the horizontal ones. The PGV values are much lower, around 3 cm/s, for all components. D_{5-95} for this station is around 50 s, whereas HI reaches 25 cm. The recorded response spectrum for this station is compared against the design spectra for rock and stiff soil conditions, sites B and C. It is observed that the recorded values are below both design spectra at all period ranges.

Finally, the station NGU is located at a lower elevation of 70.4 m and an R_{rup} distance of 113.95 km in the fault-normal direction, west of the Sagaing fault. The PGA values are recorded as 45.00 and 58.10 cm/s^2 for the east–west and north–south components, respectively. For the Z component,

Figure 3. Station NPW: (a) acceleration time series; (b) Fourier amplitude spectrum (FAS) and observed pseudoacceleration response spectra (PSA) compared with the code spectra. The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

this value is much less, 17.65 cm/s². The PGV values are 6.20 and 8.87 cm/s for the corresponding horizontal directions. Although in the Z direction, it is almost half. The significant duration is longer at this station, reaching 65.70 and 72.20 s, mostly due to surface waves at this low elevation and longer

Figure 4. Station TGI (a) acceleration time series; (b) FAS and observed pseudoacceleration response spectra (PSA) compared with the code spectra. The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

wavetrains, whereas it is even higher, 100.40 s, in the Z direction. In terms of HI, the value is around 35 cm for both horizontal directions, and in the Z direction, it reduces to 20 cm. When the response spectrum is compared with the design spectrum for site classes C and D, it is observed that the

Figure 5. Station NGU: (a) acceleration time series; (b) FAS and observed pseudoacceleration response spectra (PSA) compared with the code spectra. The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

recorded motions are much lower than the design levels. This observation is consistent with the lack of severe damage in these areas.

For the three stations, CAV values in the three components are higher than 0.16 g.s (157 cm/s), which has been identified as a conservative threshold distinguishing damaging from nondamaging ground motions for well-designed and well-constructed buildings, as defined by the MMI scale (EPRI, Palo Alto and U.S. Department of Energy, 2006).

Figure 6a shows the spatial distribution of MMI as reported by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) (2025), as well as the MMI values at the selected stations in this study. It is observed that along the fault plane toward the south of the epicenter, the MMI values reach X+, consistent with the very heavy damage in that direction. The spatial distribution of the reported MMI values also confirms the strong directivity effects observed during the 28 March 2025 Myanmar event.

Next, in Figure 6b, we compare the MMI values reported in the DYFI system (USGS, 2025) against the MMI values at the stations obtained with conversions from corresponding recorded PGA and PGV values. For conversion, we use the relationships by Bilal and Askan (2014), which were developed based on PGA and PGV using data from masonry and reinforced-concrete structures in Türkiye affected by major earthquakes. As demonstrated in the studies by Erberik (2008a,b) and later applied and validated by Karimzadeh *et al.* (2018) for Erzincan, these models were successfully verified against observed damage in regions dominated by masonry and RC building typologies. To better represent the structural typologies, both PGA and PGV values were employed, capturing the behavior of rigid masonry and more flexible reinforced-concrete structures (Erberik, 2008a,b; Karimzadeh *et al.*, 2018). The computed MMI values from these conversions show good agreement with reported observations, with only minor deviations noted at the closest NPW station. Given that Myanmar exhibits similar construction typologies, we consider the adopted equations to be reliable within an expected range of uncertainties. Furthermore, comparison with reported data demonstrates consistent agreement, as illustrated in Figure 6b.

It is observed that the computed MMI values from PGA and PGV closely match the reported data, except for minor differences in MMI values at the closest NPW station.

Secondary Hazards

Secondary effects, such as tsunamis, landslides, liquefaction, and fire, account for ~25%–40% of total economic losses and fatalities associated with earthquakes worldwide (Gómez *et al.*, 2022). Liquefaction was a dominant secondary hazard in the studied earthquake, with substantial infrastructure damage consistently attributed to its effects in prior studies. In multiple sources, severe infrastructure damage is attributed to widespread liquefaction, especially in areas south of Mandalay, such as Inwa Town, near the Irrawaddy River (e.g., National Remote

Sensing Centre, 2025), where there are local conditions, such as a shallow groundwater table, that contributed to soil instability (Wang *et al.*, 2025). Although field investigations confirmed the presence of liquefaction, this section evaluates the potential spatial extent of the phenomenon using U.S. Geological Survey (USGS, 2025) data and correlates it with various geospatial proxies. The estimated probability of liquefaction taken from USGS (2025) is based on the work of Allstadt *et al.* (2022), which is an adaptation of the model of Zhu *et al.* (2017). The model results carry substantial uncertainty because they depend on globally generalized predictor variables and ShakeMap-derived ground-motion intensities (Allstadt *et al.*, 2022), which may not fully capture local ground conditions or site-specific effects.

According to the data provided by the USGS (2025), the liquefaction probability due to this earthquake is estimated to be extensive in both severity and spatial extent. In this work, the analysis explores the relationships between geospatial proxies and the physical factors that influence liquefaction susceptibility in the Myanmar region (Fig. 7). For instance, V_{S30} serves as a proxy for soil density, as noted by Zhu *et al.* (2015), and it is a critical parameter in liquefaction analysis, as soil stiffness significantly influences liquefaction susceptibility. Higher V_{S30} values indicate stiffer soils, which are generally less prone to liquefaction compared to loose, softer soils (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2021; Cetin *et al.*, 2022). Figure 7a shows the V_{S30} distribution in the Myanmar region, based on USGS (2025) data.

As shown in Figure 7, liquefaction probability tends to be higher in areas classified as site classes E and D according to the National Earthquake Hazards Reduction Program (Building Seismic Safety Council [BSSC], 2020). The probability of liquefaction also appears elevated along the trace of the Sagaing fault. However, despite the widespread presence of softer soils in the central region, the estimated liquefaction probability is relatively low in that area, particularly on the western vertex of the Sagaing fault. In this area, the expected liquefaction probability is lower than 0.5%. This apparent anomaly may coincide with the spatial extent of geological unit TM, corresponding to the upper Pegu Group. This unit presents a north–south facies gradient that reflects a transition from nonmarine environments in the north to marine environments in the south. As a result, the deposits are characterized by thin-bedded fine to medium-grained sandstones interbedded with thick sequences of clays and siltstones, which exhibit various sedimentary structures (Ridd and Racey, 2015). The thick clay and silty layers within this geological unit are a key factor contributing to the low liquefaction susceptibility in this area. One notable observation is in Yangon City, which shows a high estimated liquefaction probability, aligning with previous findings that indicate greater vulnerability in the southern part of the city compared to the northern part (Htet *et al.*, 2018). These observations are consistent with the USGS

liquefaction map (USGS, 2025) and documented field reports (e.g., National Remote Sensing Centre, 2025).

Another relevant proxy is PGA, which is directly related to earthquake-induced loading (Zhu *et al.*, 2015). However, the relationship between PGA and liquefaction occurrence (Fig. 7b) is not straightforward. Considering the recorded PGA values,

Figure 6. (a) Spatial distribution of modified Mercalli intensity (MMI) according to U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) (USGS, 2025) along with the causative fault and the recording stations on the location map of Myanmar; (b) MMI values according to the USGS —Did You Feel It? (DYFI) (USGS, 2025) and conversion equations of Bilal and Askan (2014). The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

liquefaction probability is higher in areas located farther from the epicenter (close to Yangon City), where the observed PGA values are lower, as reported in Table 1. Near the NPW station, for example, the estimated liquefaction probability is high, which is consistent with literature suggesting that a minimum PGA of 0.10g can trigger liquefaction (Bozzoni *et al.*, 2021).

A similar analysis is conducted using recorded PGV values and liquefaction (Fig. 7c). The results are in agreement with those obtained with PGA and do not reveal a conclusive pattern. Furthermore, studies have shown that CAV, which is related to velocity, correlates well with liquefaction triggering

Figure 7. Geospatial proxies related to the probability of liquefaction in the Myanmar region: (a) V_{S30} map used as a proxy for soil stiffness; (b) estimated liquefaction probability map and the correlation with PGA; (c) estimated liquefaction probability map and the correlation with PGV; and (d) estimated liquefaction probability map and the correlation with cumulative absolute velocity (CAV). The color bars in each subplot represent the intensity of ground-motion parameters (PGA, PGV, and CAV) recorded at each station. The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

at the site-specific scale (Kramer and Mitchell, 2006; Bray and Macedo, 2017). The recorded CAV values in Figure 7d show patterns that appear more consistent with the spatial distribution of the estimated liquefaction probability. This indicates that CAV may provide complementary insights into earthquake-induced loading in this context, although it should be interpreted cautiously, given that both CAV and the liquefaction probabilities are model-derived rather than direct field observations.

Finally, it is important to recognize the uncertainties in the USGS liquefaction model (USGS, 2025), particularly in the context of Myanmar. Fluvial deposits, variable groundwater conditions, and the absence of locally calibrated data strongly influence liquefaction occurrence. As a result, these limitations may lead to either underestimation or overestimation of the actual hazard.

Observation of Building and Road Damages Using SAR Remote Sensing

To assess the extent of damage in the affected area, three ALOS-2 SAR Single Look Complex (SLC) images in ScanSAR mode are used. Two preseismic and one postseismic images from descending orbits are acquired. The acquisition dates for the preseismic images are 16 January 2025 and 19 February 2025, whereas the acquisition date of the postseismic image is 30 March 2025. Although the temporal baselines of the images are not too short, their L-band (~24 cm) capabilities in tall vegetation areas, and large footprint coverage will be an ideal tool for a rapid and reliable Interferometric SAR (InSAR) analysis. SAR systems, with their distinct all-weather, day-and-night imaging capabilities, present a significant advantage for disaster monitoring, circumventing the limitations imposed by cloud cover or darkness that often impede optical remote sensing (Ghasemi *et al.*, 2021). Among SAR-based techniques, InSAR coherence analysis, which quantifies temporal surface changes through interferometric phase correlation measurements, has demonstrated significant potential for assessing earthquake-induced structural damage (Karimzadeh and Matsuoka, 2021). Coherence, which is the normalized complex correlation coefficient from two SAR images acquired at different times, is sensitive to physical changes on the ground surface (Ghasemi *et al.*, 2021). A significant reduction in coherence (decorrelation) directly indicates physical disturbances, such as ground deformation, structural damage, or vegetation changes, which are not completely observable in SAR intensity maps (Ghasemi *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the coherence is suitable enough for identifying earthquake-induced damages, ranging from building collapse to surface ruptures and road destruction (Ghasemi *et al.*, 2021).

In this section, we aim to provide a comprehensive and spatially explicit assessment of earthquake-induced damage to both built-up areas and essential linear infrastructure (i.e., roads) in the affected areas in Myanmar, after the 28 March

2025 earthquake. We employ a differential coherence analysis approach to precisely map and quantify damage patterns. Furthermore, we analyze backscattering characteristics (i.e., intensity) and their correlation to complement the coherence-based damage detection. The derived damage maps and quantitative assessments provide key insights to support emergency response, resource allocation, and post-disaster recovery using remote sensing.

For change detection and interferometric analysis, multiple SAR images must be co-registered to ensure identical spatial dimensions and pixel correspondence. To achieve precise pixel-to-pixel matching, one image is designated as the master image while subsequent acquisitions serve as slave images in the co-registration process. The ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 imaging geometry follows the standard side-looking SAR configuration, where the range coordinate represents the slant range distance from the sensor to the target, and the azimuth coordinate corresponds to the satellite's flight path direction. These radar coordinates differ fundamentally from conventional geographic coordinate systems, necessitating geometric transformation for cartographic applications (Tamkuan and Nagai, 2017; Ghasemi *et al.*, 2021). ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 images exhibit significant geometric distortions in the range direction, primarily attributed to topographic relief displacement and the inherent slant-range imaging geometry. These distortions manifest as foreshortening in areas facing the sensor, layover in steep terrain slopes toward the radar, and shadowing in areas blocked from radar illumination (Shimada *et al.*, 2014; Karimzadeh and Matsuoka, 2021).

Consequently, radiometric calibration and coordinate system transformation from radar geometry to geographic coordinates are essential preprocessing steps. The geometric rectification process employs a backward geocoding approach utilizing a digital elevation model (DEM) to establish the relationship between radar coordinates and ground positions. The transformation algorithm incorporates several key parameters, including Doppler centroid frequencies, radar pulse transmission timing, and precise orbital vectors describing sensor position and velocity, and the 3D coordinates of ground scatterers (Toutin, 2004). The range-Doppler terrain correction method is commonly applied for ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 data, where the DEM is used to simulate the SAR imaging geometry and correct for topographic distortions (Santoro *et al.*, 2015; Alaska Satellite Facility, 2024). SAR coherence approach evaluates the statistical correlation of radar backscatter characteristics at identical geographical locations across different temporal epochs, providing valuable insights into surface modification patterns (Rosen *et al.*, 2000).

The coherence parameter functions as a quantitative measure of surface temporal stability, where unity values indicate minimal changes between acquisitions, whereas diminished values reflect substantial surface modifications during the observation period (Dieter and Bamler, 1994; Touzi *et al.*,

1999). This characteristic renders coherence analysis particularly effective for rapid damage assessment and continuous change monitoring applications in seismic contexts (Hoffmann, 2007). The interferometric coherence (γ) between two temporally separated SAR acquisitions can be mathematically defined according to the following equation (Lee *et al.*, 1994; Seymour and Cumming, 1994):

$$\gamma = \frac{E\langle ab^* \rangle}{\sqrt{E\langle aa^* \rangle E\langle bb^* \rangle}} \quad (1)$$

According to Karimzadeh and Matsuoka (2021), a and b represent the relatively complex values of the master and slave images, respectively, used in interferometric analysis. The asterisk (*) denotes the complex conjugates of the images. E represents the expectation operator. To isolate the pure phase changes caused by seismic activity, the authors remove the topographic phase using a 30-m DEM from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, whereas atmospheric noise is mitigated using established atmospheric models (Tamkuan and Nagai, 2017; Liu *et al.*, 2024).

Vegetated areas typically exhibit low coherence due to leaf growth and the random motion of tree foliage influenced by environmental factors such as wind. In contrast, urban environments maintain stable backscatter properties, as short-term effects like wind-induced movement are negligible. Consequently, higher coherence values are expected in urban regions (Karimzadeh and Matsuoka, 2021). In this study, we conducted a multitemporal coherence analysis using both ascending and descending ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 datasets to visualize the affected regions. The differential coherence method quantifies temporal stability by comparing preseismic and coseismic coherence maps for each acquisition geometry, as defined in the following equation:

$$\gamma_{\text{diff}} = \gamma_{\text{pre}} - \gamma_{\text{post}} \quad (2)$$

Positive γ_{diff} values indicate coherence degradation likely caused by seismic-induced changes, whereas negative values may suggest increased coherence due to postevent stabilization or vegetation growth. A high coherence value indicates minimal surface change, whereas a low value reflects significant alterations (Karimzadeh *et al.*, 2022).

The study region (as shown in Fig. 1) is selected as the primary focus due to its documented seismic activity and the considerable impact sustained during the 28 March 2025 Myanmar earthquake. The study area's heterogeneous landscape, characterized by a mix of densely populated urban centers, sprawling rural areas, and varied topography, provides an ideal setting for a comprehensive evaluation of earthquake-induced damage across diverse land cover and infrastructure types.

Complementary datasets were employed to refine the analysis and constrain the investigation into anthropogenic

structures. Global Urban Footprint generated from TerraSAR-X data and SAR speckle divergence analysis was applied for urban masking. This mask allowed for the systematic exclusion of vegetated and purely rural regions, where coherence loss might be attributable to environmental factors rather than structural damage. In addition, road network data from OpenStreetMap (OSM) was integrated as vector layers. These layers served dual purposes: as essential spatial references for accurately locating and analyzing damage, and as specific indicators for identifying affected linear transportation infrastructure. The integration of OSM data significantly improved the precision of interpreting differential coherence losses along transportation corridors, facilitating a more targeted identification of damaged road segments.

All datasets were geometrically co-registered to the WGS 84/UTM zone 46 N coordinate system (covering Myanmar) and resampled to a 10-m spatial resolution for consistent coherence comparison and map visualization. ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 SLC images backscattering coefficients and interferometric coherence values revealed significant insights into the earthquake-induced damage patterns for both road networks and building structures within the study area.

Figure 8a,b presents the histograms and scatter plots illustrating the distribution and correlation of backscattering coefficients for the road segments and buildings, respectively. For road segments (Fig. 9a), the average preseismic backscattering coefficient is 72.46 (standard deviation = 3.65), which increased to 73.59 postseismically. The scatter plot correlating preseismic and coseismic backscattering for roads exhibited a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.60. This relatively high R^2 indicates a strong linear relationship between backscattering values before and after the event, suggesting that while changes occurred, a general trend in backscattering properties is maintained across road segments. Similarly, for buildings (Fig. 8b), the average preseismic backscattering is 69.28, increasing to 70.85 (standard deviation = 3.96) postseismically. The corresponding R^2 for building backscattering is 0.65, denoting a moderate-to-strong correlation. These observed increases in average backscattering, despite robust correlations, are not exclusively physical changes in the ground surface and infrastructure elements. Figure 8c provides the spatial representation of these backscattering coefficients, illustrating the intensity of radar returns (brighter pixels for higher backscattering) and areas of decorrelation.

Figure 9a,b illustrates the histograms and scatter plots of coherence values for the road segments and buildings, respectively. For road networks (Fig. 9a), the average preseismic coherence is 0.48 (standard deviation = 0.16), showing a slight decrease to 0.38 coseismically. The correlation between preseismic and coseismic coherence for roads yielded an R^2 of 0.29. Conversely, for building structures (Fig. 9b), the average preseismic coherence is 0.60, which slightly decreased to 0.49 coseismically (standard deviation = 0.17). Critically, the

corresponding R^2 for building coherence is slightly higher at 0.39. These relatively low R^2 values for road segments and buildings are a direct indicator of substantial decorrelation between the preseismic and coseismic acquisitions, a hallmark of severe physical disturbance and damage to structures. They also suggest that the preseismic coherence values are poor predictors of coseismic coherence, primarily due to the widespread decorrelation induced by seismic activity. Finally, Figure 9c provides the spatial representation of coherence values, illustrating the intensity of radar returns (brighter pixels for higher backscattering) and areas of decorrelation.

Figure 8. (a) Histogram of backscattering and the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the road network in the study area. (b) Histogram of backscattering and R^2 for the buildings in the study area. (c) Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) intensity images. The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

Spatial Visualization of Building and Road Damage

The spatially explicit possible damage maps for roads (Fig. 10a) and buildings (Fig. 10b), generated through the differential

coherence analysis, further elucidate the extent and spatial distribution of earthquake-induced damage. Both maps utilize a consistent color scale, where green represents areas with no observable change, yellow signifies moderate damage, and red corresponds to heavy damage. By visually comparing Figure 10a (possible road damage) and Figure 10b (possible

Figure 9. (a) Histogram of coherence and the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the road network in the study area. (b) Histogram of coherence and R^2 for the buildings in the study area. (c) Preseismic coherence and coseismic coherence. The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

building damage), a pronounced spatial overlap of high-damage areas is observed. This overlap is particularly striking within the urban centers and densely populated regions, notably exemplified in the magnified insets. In these areas, both road networks and building structures exhibit extensive yellow

Figure 10. (a) Possible damage/change the map of the roads in the study area. (b) Possible damage/change the map of the buildings in the study area. The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

TABLE 2

Quantitative Summary of Earthquake-Induced Possible Damage to Roads and Buildings

Possible Damage	Road (km)	Building (km ²)
No damage	74,918	503.41
Moderate damage	35,019	205.12
Heavy damage	3,960	100.36

to red pixel classifications, indicating widespread and severe infrastructure damage. The linear patterns of damage visible in Figure 10a along road segments, coupled with the concentrated clusters of damaged buildings in Figure 10b, collectively confirm the devastating impact of the earthquake on the interconnected urban fabric.

Table 2 provides a comprehensive quantitative summary of the classified damage levels for both road networks and building structures within the study area. The analysis revealed that a substantial 3,960 km of roads sustained heavy damage, with an additional 35,019 km experiencing possible moderate damage. Conversely, 74,918 km of roads were categorized as having no observable damage. For buildings, the extent of damage is equally significant. A total of 100.36 km² of built-up areas were classified as possibly heavily damaged, and 205.12 km² as possibly moderately damaged. In contrast, 503.41 km² of buildings exhibited no discernible damage. The spatial distribution of the damaged areas from analyses of SAR data is observed to be consistent with the distribution of ground motions. These quantitative metrics, derived from the differential coherence analysis, corroborate the visual interpretations from the potential damage maps, providing approximate numerical values for the extent of earthquake-induced infrastructure devastation. The cumulative extent of severe and moderate damage highlights the critical need for large-scale recovery and reconstruction efforts. Although direct validation of the damage estimates was not feasible due to the absence of detailed ground observations, the coherence-based method employed here has been widely applied and validated in previous earthquakes (Karimzadeh and Mastuoka, 2017; Adriano *et al.*, 2018; Hasanlou *et al.*, 2021; Karimzadeh *et al.*, 2022), demonstrating its robustness for post-disaster damage mapping.

Although the SAR-based coherence analysis provides valuable insights into the spatial distribution of damage, several sources of uncertainty should be considered. First, temporal baselines between SAR acquisitions can pose decorrelation unrelated to structural damage, particularly when acquisition intervals are long. Second, vegetation dynamics, especially in periurban zones, may reduce coherence and complicate damage discrimination. Third, radar imaging geometry effects (layover, shadowing, and foreshortening) may obscure heavily affected structures in dense urban or mountainous regions.

Finally, the lack of extensive field data limited our ability to directly validate the coherence-derived results.

Despite these limitations, the methodology has been extensively tested in prior seismic events and has consistently demonstrated reliable performance in identifying damaged areas. In this context, the observed agreement between the spatial distribution of strong ground motions and our coherence-based damage estimates provides confidence that the results presented in Table 2 represent a robust first-order approximation of actual damage patterns.

Conclusions

Analysis of the recorded seismic data from the 28 March 2025 Myanmar earthquake revealed strong directivity effects and high ground-motion parameters, particularly at near-field stations located in the forward rupture direction and on softer soil conditions. The recorded spectra at the near-field station exceeded the Myanmar National Building Code values for short periods, which may explain the widespread damage to low-rise buildings.

Liquefaction was one of the most prominent secondary hazards, especially in areas with soft soil conditions and shallow groundwater, such as near the Irrawaddy River. The relationship between CAV and estimated liquefaction probability appeared to be more consistent than PGA or PGV alone, indicating its potential as a better proxy for rapid postevent liquefaction assessment.

Through advanced SAR-based coherence analysis, we were able to detect and map extensive infrastructure damage. The results indicated that over 39,000 km of roads and 306 km² of built-up areas suffered moderate-to-heavy damage. The coherence-based damage mapping method proved particularly useful for highlighting changes in urban areas, with strong agreement between building and road damage zones, also consistent with the spatial distribution of ground motions.

Overall, this study underscores the importance of integrating strong-motion data, secondary hazard modeling, and remote sensing in postearthquake damage assessments. The insights gained can inform future emergency response planning and seismic risk mitigation strategies for Myanmar and other tectonically active regions.

Data and Resources

All data used in this article came from published sources listed in the references.

Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors acknowledge that there are no conflicts of interest recorded.

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